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AN ACTOR-NETWORK RESEARCH FRAME FOR ANALYSING COMPLEX SOCIO-TECHNICAL SITUATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a “research frame” which we have found useful in analyzing complex socio-technical situations. The research frame is based on aspects of actor-network theory: “interressment”, “enrollment”, “points of passage” and the “trial of strength”. Each of these aspects are described in turn, making clear their purpose in the overall research frame. Having established the research frame it is used to analyse two examples. First, the use of speech recognition technology is examined in two different contexts, showing how to apply the frame to compare and contrast current situations. Next, a current medical consultation context is described and the research frame is used to consider how it could change with innovative technology. In both examples, the research frame shows that the use of an artefact or technology must be considered together with the context in which it is used.

Keywords: field studies, actor-network, context, design.

INTRODUCTION

An actor-network approach can be a useful way to understand complex socio-technical situations that are of interest to designers. However, actor-network theory can be difficult to engage with. This paper presents an actor-network approach that we have found is useful for framing analysis of complex socio-technical situations. The paper has four sections.

First we give a brief introduction to what we think is most useful about actor-network theory (ANT). Then we describe our specific framework for the application of actor-network theory to design

research problems. The application of the framework is shown through two examples. Finally, we reflect on the framework itself the way it can change how we consider artefacts that are not yet designed.

An actor-network approach has become more common in design research (Ben Shaw, 2009; Ricci, 2010; Schneider, Richter, & Petzold, 2010) and related fields, particular in information systems (Tatnall, 2003; Walsham, 1997) and human-computer interaction (Gartner, 1996). One reason ANT has found favour in design-related fields is its ability to deal with human and non-human elements simultaneously by considering them symmetrically, as being equally able to influence a situation. This aspect of ANT has also been one of the most widely criticized (eg Kaptelinin and Nardi (2006)). However, the stance that in certain situations things can have as much or more power than people is a useful perspective to take, especially when trying to understand how a new thing can change an existing situation if everything else remains, initially, the same. We use this as our starting point for the development of our actor-network framework which is specifically made for considering how the introduction of a new artefact can change an existing situation.

In actor-network terms, taking an “actor” from one network and inserting it into another is called translation. Actor-network theory is especially interested in how a things change in relation to other things. It sometimes been referred to as a sociology of translation.

THE SOCIOLOGY OF TRANSLATION

Actor-Network Theory is an approach developed in Science and Technology Studies for analysing the interplay between social systems and technologies. It is particularly useful for describing “the small, concrete technical and non-technical mechanisms which go into the building and use” (Monteiro & Hanseth, 1995) of socio-technical systems. The purpose of doing an actor-network analysis is to describe the elements of a situation that make it unique and to identify how those elements remain in a particular arrangement rather than splitting apart.

At the beginning of an actor-network analysis, all the elements of the situation are given equal weight. In the language of STS this is called treating actors (or actants as they are sometimes called) symmetrically (Callon, 1986). In performing this kind of analysis, actants are any thing, person, artefact, social situation or political fact that could have some power in a situation. That is, before the analysis has shown otherwise, any person or non-human entity of interest is considered to have the ability to change a situation. This stance has been one of the major sources of criticism of the actor-network approach (Kaptelinin & Nardi, 2006).

The purpose of this paper is to work through two examples of ANT analysis using our framework to demonstrate how an ANT analysis is done. ANT is especially useful for analysing how power is directed and used which makes it useful as a lens through which to structure analysis of existing and future socio-technical situations. Since design is, in many cases, concerned with creating new situations involving artefacts, systems of use and social elements, an actor-network approach can be appropriate for design research purposes.

The following two case studies demonstrate the use of an actor-network approach derived from Callon’s (Callon, 1986) “sociology of translation” which uses four “moments of translation” to frame analysis. Callon describes how three marine biologists attempted to develop a conservation strategy for scallops in St Brieuc Bay in Normandy. Other actor-network theorists have used to approach in a great variety of domains and have emphasized different

aspects of ANT in their analyses. Law, for example, emphasizes “difference” (Law, 2006) while Latour examines “tracing associations” in, for example, the ways new rapid transit system failed to be introduced (Latour, 1996). We use Callon’s work as the root of our approach because the four-step method makes it easy to work through. We show how the steps interrelate and how the actor-network stance is applied. The steps Callon describes are:

1. Problemetisation
2. Interessment
3. Enrollment
4. Mobilisation.

Figure 1: Callon’s “moments of translation” (Callon, 1986)

In the problemetisation step, an actor or group of actors (the marine biologists) tries to make themselves indispensable to the other actors in the story (the fishermen, the scallops, the local economy, etc). The interessment step and enrollment step describe how the researchers tried to direct the other actors to follow the roles assigned to them by the researchers. Finally, the mobilisation step describes how the researchers managed the new relations between the actors.

Other actor-network theorists have identified different ways to consider how networks become assembled and how they stay together. A synthesis of these approaches is described below.

AN ACTOR-NETWORK RESEARCH FRAME

The research frame we present builds on Callon’s sociology of translation and uses terminology from Callon and Latour. The questions in the research frame are not linear but are, in every actor-network, constantly in play. The shift from Callon’s “sociology of translation” to the research frame is in keeping with an actor-network stance since the shift rebalances the ANT approach for the purposes of design research. Callon’s purpose was to demonstrate the translation approach; our purpose here is to show how to adapt that approach for design research. The four steps in our approach are shown in table 1.

Step	Name	Concern
1	Interestment	which actors and actants are in the network?
2	Enrollment	what roles are those actors and actants given
3	Points of Passage	which actor is trying to direct, control and manage the others
4	Trial of Strength	how does the arrangement of actors hold together and how strong or fragile is the arrangement

Table 1: An Actor-Network Research Frame

Callon's first step, problematisation, is skipped in this approach. In Callon's work, actors seeking to change an existing situation are identified in the problematisation step. In the research frame analysis we are concerned with an established situation where the problematisation has already occurred or with a future situation into which designers are attempting to insert themselves.

In the interestment step, actors are made interested in joining an actor-network. The way in which those individual actors are made interested is unique to the particular actor-network.

In the enrollment step, actors agree to play a role in the network and they are translated into the network and inscribed with a program of action (Akrich, 1992). Put another way, actors who join a network are given a script to follow. Although the concepts of roles and scripts are generally interchangeable, we will use the term role to describe this concept.

In any network, one or more actors may attempt to establish themselves as a point of passage. The point of passage is the actor who assigns roles to, or acts as a spokesperson for, the other actors in the network. Conflicts arise in an actor-network when more than one actor attempts to establish themselves as a point of passage. Another source of conflict can be when an actor who tries to be a point of passage cannot enrol enough actors and actants in their program of action.

In the trial of strength actors follow, or do not follow, the roles assigned to them. If all the actors in the network follow their assigned roles, then the network is stable. If one or more actors do not follow their assigned role, the network is unstable. Unstable networks either fall apart, and are replaced by more stable networks, or are actively held together through the efforts of one or more actors. The relative stability of an actor-network determines the work required to establish a new actor in the network. Stable networks are almost self-sustaining, requiring little effort on the part of the actors who have a stake in the network's continued existence. Unstable networks require much effort to sustain in the face of other competing networks. When actors stop following their assigned roles, an actor-network fails.

To show how the research frame is used, two case studies are described below. As Law points out, one way to represent an actor-network approach is to perform it, rather than describe its "fundamental rules" (Law, 2006). By working through the research frame we show how to apply it as well as demonstrating its effectiveness in analyzing complex situations of use.

EXAMPLE 1: SPEECH RECOGNITION SOFTWARE

In this example, we describe how two different contexts where people use speech recognition are examined. In the first context, individuals brought speech recognition to their workplace because they had chronic injuries that made it impossible to type at a keyboard. In the second context, speech recognition had already been integrated into the workplace by the management.

These two contexts are then analysed together for the factors that allow speech recognition to be used successfully.

CASE A: WORKPLACE OVERUSE INJURIES IN THE AUSTRALIAN FEDERAL PUBLIC SERVICE

People who develop certain kinds of workplace overuse injury, for example RSI, find it extremely painful to type or use a mouse. For many people, a break from computer use and some physical therapy

can repair their injury. Sometimes, the injury recurs so often that there is no solution other than ceasing to use a keyboard and mouse. In some cases, health-care providers will recommend, or an injured person may experiment with, adopting speech recognition software in order to return to work.

For the injured users in this context, returning to work with the use of speech recognition software becomes an ongoing problem because using a computer through speech recognition is not simply a matter of speaking instead of typing. Using a computer through speech input is a distinct skill, which must be learned. Dictating text is only one aspect of using ASR. Users must also learn to control programs and replace mousing actions with speech commands. They must also learn to correct errors -- both their own errors and mistakes made by the software (Read, MacFarlane, & Casey, 2002). Error correction with ASR is a difficult interaction design problem (Feng & Sears, 2010; CA Halverson, DB Horn, & Karat, 1999; Karat, C Halverson, & D Horn, 1999) but is far from the only challenge in using ASR successfully in the workplace.

The injured users had many problems to overcome before they could be productive in their workplace. Some had computers that were not powerful enough to run the speech recognition software. Others worked in noisy offices that interfered with the software's ability to accurately transcribe speech. Still others had switched jobs so they could work in roles that were compatible with the capabilities of the speech recognition software they used.

Each of the injured users of ASR was compelled to be constantly vigilant about the security of the assemblage of artefacts that made their work possible. Because of their relatively low status in their organisations, maintaining that control was difficult. This was especially clear when seen in comparison to a second case study with speech recognition users who were uninjured and used ASR without concern for the place of the software in their work.

CASE B: NON-INJURED ASR USERS

The non-injured users of speech recognition worked in an office of the Department of Parliamentary Services that produces "Hansard", the record of all that is said in the representative chambers and committees in Australia's Federal Parliament House.

Hansard is produced every day and requires the transcription of everything said in the House of Representatives, the Senate and various committees staffed by elected representatives. Until recently, Hansard editors used computer-assisted transcription (CAT) machines, which use a chording keyboard to facilitate extremely fast typing. Chording keyboards are also used in courtroom transcription. A fully trained CAT user has highly specialised skills and can command a high salary. The Hansard editors seen in the case study used ASR instead of CAT. None had used ASR before beginning with the Hansard office but were trained in less than six months to a level of proficiency that made it possible for them to work at the speed necessary for their work. This compared very favourably for the Hansard office with the very long training time for CAT, which is often more than a year for a novice.

Regardless of the transcription tool used, the work process is largely the same. Each editor is assigned a number of small parts of a day's proceedings to transcribe. Once trained, an ASR-using Hansard editor creates the transcript of their assigned parts of the day's parliamentary proceedings by re-speaking every part of the audio they were assigned. The speech recognition software does not recognize the speech of the elected members; it acts as a way to enable rapid transcription of speech by the editors. Generally an editor does one pass over the recording by re-speaking and then edits the resulting text using mouse and keyboard. Once transcribed, edited and verified for accuracy, each part of the transcript is combined into the day's Hansard.

In contrast to the injured users, the Hansard editors did not struggle to use ASR. The Hansard office's commitment to its employees' use of ASR had assumed all of the effort required to make ASR into a useful system.

ANALYSIS OF SPEECH RECOGNITION USE

Using our actor-network research frame to analyse both of these situations shows how they are different and similar.

The injured speech recognition users had to interest many elements in becoming part of a network of actors so that they could use speech recognition software. They had to bring together computer hardware and software so that they could use ASR. Many of the interviewees did not have the authority in their organisation to order their own computing resources so they had to interest and enrol their superiors into the network. Having received authorisation to acquire new hardware, many users had to then enrol their IT support providers. At the time of the study it was common for government departments to outsource their IT needs. The contracts for support generally required some form of Common User Environment which may or may not have been compatible with the needs of the ASR software, requiring more effort on the part of the injured user to bring the support contractor into their network. In cases where the outsourced IT provider had agreed to a small level of support of the ASR software the injured users reported that the providers would often try to avoid responsibility for the software's problems blaming them on the computer hardware or third-party infrastructure rather than the software or operating environment.

Throughout this process, the injured users were trying to establish themselves as the point of passage—the actor who was able to assign roles to other actors in the network. However, throughout this process, other actors were also attempting to establish their authority. For example, one participant worked for an organisation that produced policy documents. These documents were constantly and collaboratively edited. This editing process required the use of a document management system (DMS), which performed various functions including managing ownership of documents and facilitating document check-out and so on. One of the participants made it clear to her organisation that should the DMS ever be changed that she be allowed to test any proposed system with the ASR she used. She was allowed to test a proposed new system and

found it incompatible. The incompatible system was purchased anyway, effectively locking her out of the system until a work-around could be found. In this case, the new DMS became a point-of-passage because it assumed the ability to assign roles to other actors. The role the DMS assigned to potential users did not account for some workers need to use ASR. This example also shows how the ANT approach can be used to consider non-humans as actors in a network.

For injured users, the trial of strength happened every day. They found their ASR software to be quite temperamental such that if they had a cold their recognition accuracy would be lower than normal, requiring more correcting effort. This also occurred if internal changes in their organisation forced them to move office environments from a secluded office to an open-plan cubicle. Each change in the carefully orchestrated network of relations between software, hardware, office space and work practice could render them unable to work.

In contrast to the injured users, the Hansard editors did not struggle with their use of ASR.

Because the Hansard office had committed to using ASR as an input method for the production of the Hansard document, the Hansard office had brought together all of the actors required to make a stable network around ASR: microphones and computer hardware, work tasks and work practices, office layout and more. The Hansard office became the point of passage in the network, directing the various actors in the roles it had assigned for them. The trial of strength at Hansard was really no trial at all as the power of the office and its relatively vast resources, compared with the injured users, made it easy to sustain the successful use of ASR.

FEATURES FOR THE SUCCESSFUL USE OF SPEECH RECOGNITION SOFTWARE

Using our research frame to analyse the two case studies shows the practices and artefacts that must be successfully drawn into a network of relations before ASR can be used. The successful use of ASR requires not only working ASR but also adequate computing power, suitable microphones, a work

practice that fits with the capabilities of off-the-shelf ASR software, a workplace that will allow the use of ASR and an organisation that is willing to accommodate the use of ASR. Typical use cases of ASR often only account for the suitability of the software itself and neglect the other aspects such as the integration of the software with a users work and work process.

Using the research frame to analyse the use of ASR shows that the successful use of the software depends on more than the capabilities of the software. The research frame is an approach that identifies wider connections that must be created and maintained between the artefact of interest -- ASR -- and aspects of the wider context. Having identified these connections the research frame then directs attention to which actor (or actant) is directing the situation or attempting to direct it. Finally, having identified the actors, actants and roles in the network, the research frame then asks how and if the network stays together.

In the ASR case studies, the research frame is used to compare and contrast two similar case studies. In the next example, the research frame is used to analyse an existing situation and to think about a possible future situation.

EXAMPLE 2: PRE-SURGICAL ANAESTHETIC CONSULTATIONS

In this example we examined the ways that anaesthetists use stethoscopes in surgical pre-admission consultations. Our purpose was to consider the implications of using a digital stethoscope over a video-conferencing link as part of a pre-admission consultation. It has become common in the medical field to call such consultations “telehealth”. In order to describe the telehealth case, we first describe the “normal” in-person interaction of a face-to-face consultation between an anaesthetist and a patient.

CASE A: FACE-TO-FACE CONSULTATIONS

A pre-admission consultation takes place in the Australian public healthcare system approximately a week before a scheduled surgery. The patient meets with an anaesthetist, who is a medical doctor, to discuss their upcoming anaesthesia. The pre-

admission consultation only deals with the anaesthetic aspects of the patient’s upcoming surgery. The surgeon and other specialists are not present for the consultation. The purpose of the consultation is to ascertain whether the patient has any preexisting conditions that may interfere with the anaesthesia and so prevent the surgery taking place. The consultation takes place in the hospital in a special clinic. Patients are scheduled for a particular time and are first examined by a nurse who collects various measurements (weight, height, blood pressure), which are important in calculating the anaesthetic dose. After seeing the nurse, the patient sees an anaesthetist. The anaesthetist the patient sees is not necessarily the one who will attend the patient on the day of their surgery so the outcomes of the consultation are documented on a special form that becomes part of the patient’s medical record.

Most of the consultation between doctor and patient involves the doctor asking the patient questions about their general health and their previous experiences with anaesthesia. The questions are intended to allow the doctor to determine if the patient can be anaesthetised and the surgery can go ahead.

A small part of the consultation involves a physical examination of the patient. For most patients this examination consists of the doctor listening to the patient’s chest with a stethoscope, a process known as auscultation, and a brief inspection of the patient’s mouth and airway. The auscultation verifies that the patient has no unexpected heart condition and the inspection of the mouth and airway allows the doctor to note any abnormalities that may impede resuscitation, for example dentures.

The auscultation takes place extremely quickly during the physical examination. In many cases that were observed the entire physical examination takes two minutes in a twenty-minute consultation with the auscultation taking less than 60 seconds. The longest physical examinations observed were of patients who had previous heart conditions and were being examined for future heart operations.

In addition to the face-to-face consultations we observed, we also saw several consultations conducted using existing telehealth infrastructure.

CASE B: EXISTING TELEHEALTH CONSULTATIONS

The telehealth consultations we observed did not involve a telehealth stethoscope (which did not exist at the time of the fieldwork and only exists as a limited prototype at the time of writing). In the current system, telehealth consultations take place if two criteria are met. First, patients seen via telehealth live too far away from the hospital to travel in for a short consultation and second they are classified as “low risk”. In this context a “low risk” patient is one who is generally healthy and is only having a regional anaesthetic for their upcoming procedure. If, for example, a patient is “high risk” and lives a great distance from the hospital, they must travel to the hospital for their consultation. In some cases they must stay overnight near the hospital, often at their own expense. Some patients observed travelled for more than 3 hours for a 20 minute consultation before traveling 3 hours home.

In analysing the activity that took place in the face-to-face consultations and the telehealth consultations, it became apparent that with the exception of the auscultation, the consultations were the same. That some consultations can take place without physical contact between doctor and patient shows how the form holds the other elements together even in the absence of the stethoscope which we had thought was essential to the process.

ACTORS, ACTANTS AND THEIR ROLES

The effortless way that the doctors conducted the auscultation in the face-to-face consultations can be examined in many ways, for example for the use of tacit knowledge (Kraal & Popovic, 2010a), or the specific actions involved in the process however the research frame provides another way to consider auscultation in the preadmission consultation context.

The interestment step identifies the potential actors in the network. The entire hospital infrastructure is

in many ways essential to the process as is the public health system and the way it is enacted to require the use of preadmission clinics. However, considering the preadmission clinic in a smaller context also shows how many elements are required to come together successfully so that the auscultation can happen. Doctor, patient, stethoscope, the sounds transmitted by the stethoscope, the rooms where the consultation takes place and even the documents that the doctor on which the doctor records their notes must be “enrolled”.

The enrollment step describes how the elements come together. The patient and doctor must be co-located. The doctor must be familiar with his or her stethoscope and the ways to acquire and understand the sounds transmitted from the patient’s chest. The sounds heard through a stethoscope are very subtle and it requires much effort to learn to interpret them correctly and much practice to maintain the knowledge of how to understand the sounds. The doctor must know how to place the stethoscope on the patient’s body in order to obtain the sounds. The patient must submit to being touched by the doctor, often by partially undressing (and in the case of the field work, they must submit to partially undressing in front of a researcher and a camera, too!). The forms provided to the doctor must allow adequate recording of the interpretation of the chest sounds.

The point of passage, that is, the actor in the assemblage that attempts, and succeeds, to control the situation is difficult to identify. Considering the situation at the infrastructural level, the hospital, as part of the public health system, is the point of passage as it is in the hospital’s interest to ensure that the patient can be anesthetized at the time of their operation, rather than lose the money associated with preparing an operating theatre and the associated personnel for procedure that does not go ahead.

It could be said that the point of passage is the position of power held by the doctor, however an actor-network view would question that perspective as it argues that the agency of the doctor in the preadmission context is produced through the relationships between the other actors and actants.

An actor-network perspective tries to figure out what is it about the situation that allows the doctor to act with power in the situation.

Considering the preadmission clinic only within the bounds of what takes place in the consultation room itself, it is *not* the doctor who is the point of passage even though he or she directs the consultation. The point of passage is not the actor who is in charge but rather the actor, or actant, that directs the other actors and holds them together in the network. Unlike the injured ASR users who constantly struggled to make their software useful, the doctor's position is much more like that of the Hansard ASR users who benefited from their organisation's efforts at removing the barriers to success. Where the Hansard organisation provided a work practice that matched the capabilities of ASR, in this case the work is directed by the purpose of the consultation itself and, to an extent, the form that the doctors must fill out as they work through the consultation. Other elements are also brought in to the network to allow the doctor manage the consultation including the doctor's extensive training and expertise. But it is the consultation form and the purpose the form represents that directs the actors and holds them together. That this is the case can be seen in the trial of strength.

The trial of strength, that is the test that the entire assemblage of actors in the network endures, occurs in the interaction between doctor and patient. All of the elements in the network are stabilized by the purpose of the consultation. As long as the individual doctor and patient play the roles assigned them by the consultation, the other elements can be co-opted into the network as needed. The purpose of the consultation is so powerful that it takes a lot to destabilize the network of actors in the consultation.

In the case of the preadmission clinic, one way the consultation form can be seen to direct the other actors is when the doctor ignores the patient in favour of the medical record and the form. On several occasions, one of the participant doctors told a patient, "just a minute and I will get the information I need from your paperwork". Some of the patients observed had travelled for several hours

for their consultation and spent some of it watching a doctor copy information from one file to another. There are, of course, other reasons why this (lack of) interaction occurs but the primacy of the consultation form in can be seen in telehealth examples, too.

In telehealth consultations' that we observed the anaesthetists were able to conduct the consultation in much the same way as a face-to-face consultation. As with the face-to-face consultations, it was common for the doctor to spend as much time with the administrative aspects of the consultation as in communicating with the patient. We had expected, in line with videoconferencing literature, to see reduced communication in the telehealth cases. We could not locate any difference in the communication between doctor and patient in our analysis of the telehealth consultations and the face-to-face consultations. The research frame suggests that there is some actor in the telehealth consultation that allows it to be so similar to the face-to-face consultation. In our analysis the consultation form remained the point-of-passage in the telehealth case. Additionally, the classification of patients as "low risk" allowed the physical examination to be skipped in the telehealth case. Two non-human actors, the consultation form and the classification of patient risk permit current telehealth consultations to take place.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE DESIGN OF A TELEHEALTH STETHOSCOPE

In the telehealth situation the doctor is not currently compelled to use a stethoscope. In the face-to-face situation, the doctor is able to use their stethoscope intuitively (Kraal & Popovic, 2010b; 2010a). That telehealth consultations can currently take place seems to indicate that the doctors would be able to ignore any future telehealth stethoscope if they felt it was not useful. The classification of patients as high risk could also be used to, quite sensibly, justify bringing remote patients in to the hospital even with a telehealth stethoscope facility.

A telehealth stethoscope must be, obviously, adequate for use in a preadmission context. But, the presence of a telehealth stethoscope that is not all

that must change before more remote consultations can take place.

Using the research frame it is possible to speculate about the use of a telehealth stethoscope in a remote preadmission context. The context is largely the same as current telehealth consultations. The telehealth stethoscope requires a number of changes to the interaction between doctor and patient. First, because self-auscultation is difficult for untrained people (Fragasso et al., 2007), a nurse is required to attend the patient and place the head of the telehealth stethoscope. Second, the telehealth stethoscope itself is different to an ordinary stethoscope. These two differences are considered below.

Instead of being able to touch the patient, the doctor must view them on a television screen and a nurse must place the stethoscope head on the patient's chest. Instead of two relationships to manage (doctor-patient and patient-doctor) a telehealth consultation has six (doctor-patient, doctor-nurse, nurse-patient, nurse-doctor, patient-doctor and patient-nurse). How these relationships and the work practices that will be necessary are managed are the focus of our ongoing research.

Additionally, instead of a simple mechanical stethoscope, a telehealth stethoscope is a complicated signal-processing computer which transforms sound waves into compressed digital signals, sends them down copper wires or optical fibers, de-compresses them and turns them back into sound waves.

The fragility of the telehealth stethoscope in the preadmission context is not known. The reliability of an acoustic stethoscope can be taken for granted but a telehealth stethoscope is a new technology that has not been proven. But the telehealth stethoscope is actually a complicated assemblage of stethoscope bell-and-diaphragm head, microphone, analogue-to-digital converter, signal processing unit and amplifiers, and the entire telehealth infrastructure. If any one element of the telehealth stethoscope infrastructure fails, the entire stethoscope fails. This is itself a significant design problem. Not only should

a telehealth stethoscope be as much like an ordinary stethoscope as possible, but in the case of a breakdown in functionality it must be easy to diagnose a wide range of connectivity and sound quality problems.

Finally, the classification of patients as high or low risk is what currently determines whether a telehealth consultation takes place at all. Without reassessment of the risk criteria, even with the presence of a telehealth stethoscope, a wider range of telehealth preadmission consultations will not take place.

This analysis shows the power of the research frame for understanding the future use of new artefacts because it suggests that the telehealth stethoscope will not affect preadmission consultation practice without the creation of new work practices and without new procedures for assessing patient's suitability for remote consultations.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented a new research frame for considering existing socio-technical situations. Our research frame draws heavily on aspects of actor-network theory, particularly aspects which deal with how arrangements of technology, people, processes and things come about and are sustained. A particular strength of our research frame is that it can be used to analyse which aspects of an existing situation are the most important - which aspects of a situation are a point-of-passage. By showing which aspects of an existing situation are the most important the research frame can also be used to consider the successful integration of artefacts that are yet-to-be designed in an existing situation.

In the speech recognition case, the successful use of the disruptive technology of ASR is shown to rest with the successful integration of that technology into the wider sphere of work.

In the preadmission clinic case, we have considered how a telehealth stethoscope could be integrated into an existing work practice. We have also argued that certain procedural aspects of the existing work

practice need to be considered in parallel with the physical telehealth stethoscope.

In both cases, we argue that the design of the artefact is not enough to ensure successful use. It is the design of the situation in which the artefact is used that contributes to the success of the artefact. For the injured ASR users, their ability to design their use of the software was constrained by their lack of power in their workplaces. The Hansard case showed how much easier using ASR can be when a powerful workplace commits to a novel work practice. And the stethoscope case shows how what seems to be an essential artefact, a doctors stethoscope which is intimately tied to the perceived identity of doctors is made less essential through factors only distantly related to the stethoscope itself.

These examples and their constituent case studies and analysis have shown the power of the research frame and the suitability of an actor-network for doing design research. By describing the actors and actants in a situation and working through the roles assigned to them, the framework aids in considering all aspects of a situation that have the potential to be relevant. Actor-network theory's commitment to agnosticism regarding the difference between actors and actants makes it possible to consider how things or people may play a role in directing a situation. The research frame we have described in this paper contributes to the growing number of examples in the design research field using approaches from from science and technology studies. Our contribution demonstrates the benefits of an actor-network approach and shows how to apply that approach to analyse existing situations. A unique aspect of our approach is that we have shown it can also be used to make arguments from current practice about future practice and the use of future artefacts.

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